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Appraisal Theory as a Linguistic Tool to Analyse Jose Saramago's Blindness

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Abstract

The employment of appraisal theory into specialized literary genre studies is, in general, marked by its absence. Though it provides the possibilities for analysing what speakers or writers imply in text. Nonetheless, appraisal theory is increasingly being applied in different fields and in the examination of many texts, preceding studies have mostly isolated specific markers rather than trying for a more holistic framework (Alsina et al., 2017, pp.2-5). This study proposes that it is possible to combine approaches from critical discourse analysis with appraisal theory to broaden one's perspective on the many factors beyond the individual's control that shape an evaluation's final form and intended meaning. The data for this study was collected from Jose Saramago's *Blindness*, namely 10 extracts taken from the climax of the story. It was then analysed using Martin and White's (2005) framework of appraisal theory, in relation to Fairclough's critical discourse analysis framework (1989). This study demonstrated that appraisal framework and to Fairclough's critical discourse analysis framework (1989) can be applied to an extended fiction text. The result of the analysis exposes Saramago's Marxist beliefs through the combination of both frameworks. The findings also demonstrated that the majority of the appraisals sub-categories attributed to attitude in the data are negative judgments, rather than affect or appreciation.

Keywords: Appraisal theory, Appraisal Framework Jose Saramago, *Blindness*, apocalyptic, Systemic Functional Linguistics, Critical Discourse Analysis

1. Introduction

Language has always been a crucial component of emotional expressions (Lindquist et al., 2015, p.1). In order to comprehend emotions, scholars from different fields are required to work together, because feelings involve social norms about how, why, when, where, and to whom we express our emotions (Ataei, 2018, p.1). Appraisal theory (henceforth AT), also referred to as appraisal framework (henceforth AF), provides a discourse analytic framework to determine the relationship between emotions and evaluative language (Colombi, 2009). This framework is concerned with how text producers express their attitudes. An appraisal analysis was conducted by Yuningsih (2018) 'An Appraisal Analysis: The Interpersonal Meaning in the Discourse of a Lyric'. The study aimed at analysing interpersonal meanings and linguistics features from the perspective of 'Appraisal.' Yuningsih used a qualitative method based on White and Martin's (2005) framework. The study used the AF to analyse the messages conveyed by song lyrics of "Lonely Night" by Cnblue. According to the findings, the song "Lonely Night" has a high Affect sub-category of 81.25 %, while Judgement and Affection have the same amount of 9.3 %. The researcher was after finding how the songwriters' express feelings, how they amplify them, and how they may incorporate additional voices in their songs (Yuningsih, 2018, p.174). However, doing a partial analysis based on a part or some parts of

Published/ publié in *Res Militaris* (resmilitaris.net), vol.12, n°3, November Issue 2022

the framework properly result in ineffective application of that framework. The preceding studies have shown that the authors used certain parts of the AF to analyse the English text. For instance, the study adopted by Yuningsih (2018) only the sub-field of attitude ie judgment was selected.

Moreover, there are still many unanswered questions in the field of AT, giving researchers the opportunity to expand the framework's applicability to other types of texts (White, 2020). Modern linguistic studies in the field of AT have typically been applied to the limited scope of political speeches and debates. On the occasion that AT has been applied to fiction texts, it has been done so in a limited manner (for example, Yuningsih, 2018). Thus, the current study is an attempt to analysis an apocalyptic genre. The aim of this research is to develop a deeper understanding of appraisal framework as a linguistic tool to analyse the evaluations in fictional texts in cooperation with critical discourse analysis (henceforth CDA). This research is believed to inspire critical discourse analysts and researchers in the field of linguistics to focus on deceit discourse. It draws attention to the lies of the powerful and the truth hidden behind the texts. The implication behind this study invites CDA studies to focus on the rhetorical aspects and the evaluation that need to be interpreted. Figuring out how feelings embedded within texts effects people's view of life. Such analysis goes beyond conspiracy criticisms, it provides a clear vision of the ideologies and social realisation hidden behind texts.

2. Systemic Functional Linguistics

Systemic functional grammar (henceforth SFG) was first introduced by Halliday in his seminal work "An Introduction to Functional Grammar" (1985). (Bloor & Bloor, 2004, p.2). According to Young and Harrison (2004), SFL is a theory of study that examines how language has developed to suit various social tasks. From this vantage point, language is used in various contexts by analysing 'real'-world interactions. Through doing so, SFL seeks to understand the processes by which meaning is constructed in a range of contexts (p.1).

SFL's contention is that the structural shape of a clause in English is simultaneously determined by three metafunctions; the ideational, interpersonal and textual. In every instance of language use these three metafunctions work together to create meaning connected to the context (Halliday,1994, p.39). According to Lock (1996), the ideational function refers to the way language represents our experience. The Interpersonal metafunction is concerned with the roles and interactions between people, as well as the attitudes toward one another (Herman et. al., 2022). The textual meaning is the linguistic structure that results from the text's particular setting (p. 10).

3. Interpersonal Metafunction in SFL

A functional approach to language is based on the assumption that the language system has evolved in a functional manner. Therefore, a primary goal of communication is to build and sustain meaningful interpersonal connections with others. Communication with others serves a variety of reasons, including to influence their behaviour or attitudes, to share information with them that they do not have, to explain our own attitudes and behaviours (Thompson, 2014, p. 45). Thus, this section provides an overview of the most essential lexicogrammatical, or rather interpersonal meaning, systems used in a text to convey effective messages.

Moreover, Bloor and Bloor (2004) have stated that the interpersonal metafunction is one of the properties of language that shows how speakers engage in communicative activities with others, assume roles, express and interpret feelings, and reveal attitude and judgement (p.11).

However, Ye (2010) has mentioned that the interpersonal meaning could be realized through certain aspects of grammar. For example, the interpersonal meaning corresponds to one of the situational contexts, such as tenor. In principle, this social relation is conveyed through the realization of mood and modality (p.1). Therefore, speakers or writers express their attitudes, judgments, and opinions by choosing certain vocabularies and lexicogrammar. Eggins (2004) refers to interpersonal meanings as our roles and interactions with other people, as well as our attitudes toward one another. Regardless of the purpose for which we use language, we are always conveying an attitude and assuming a role (p.12). We may use sentence (3.1 **Peggy arrived at 8.30**) as an illustration. The interpersonal meaning of this sentence is to inform that the event took place. However, it also offers the ways we make judgments and shows our attitude towards others or objects. For example, in sentences like:

Did Peggy arrive at 8.30?

Peggy might arrive at 8.30

Both sentences (3.2) and (3.3) refer to the same person (Peggy) performing an action (arriving) at a specific time (at 8.30). Sentences (3.2) and (3.3) provide the same information as sentence (3.1). This means that they have the same ideational meaning but different interpersonal meaning. Though (3.2) is a question and (3.3) is a statement, they still have the same experiential meaning. Sentence (3.2) calls the listener to confirm or deny the event, while sentence (3.3) introduces an assessment by the speaker of the likelihood of the event having taken place. As a result, (3.2) and (3.3) differ in terms of interpersonal meaning but have the same ideational meaning (Lock,1996, p. 9).

4. Critical Discourse Analysis

Critical discourse analysts are primarily concerned with how ideas work in social life (Wodak, 2001, p. 2). A major goal of CDA is to uncover, reveal, or disclose what is implicit, hidden, or otherwise not immediately apparent in relationships of discursively enacted dominance or its underlying ideologies (Van Dijk, 1995, p.183). Therefore, CDA requires a description of linguistic qualities in order to explore the social function of language.

According to Fairclough (2013) a pioneer of CDA, ideologies can be assumptions and common sense. Implicit conventions and cultural norms are unconscious phenomena that people are not aware of. When people speak, they introduce their point of view to affect the listener or assert power. These viewpoints are hidden and become common sense to most participants. For example, when a doctor speaks with a patient, it is accepted via common sense that the doctor will ask the patient questions, placing the doctor in control of the speech (p. 2).

Explicit CDA therefore requires a strong "linguistic foundation." As claimed by Young and Harrison (2004) there are significant similarities between CDA and SFL. They both stress the importance of language in society. Likewise, they hold the same view of language as a social construct shaped by specific discursive occurrences (p. 1). Widdowson (2004) has further asserted that CDA generally obtains its descriptive cues from SFL (p.90), while Fairclough (2003) sustains that SFL is a useful resource for CDA and that significant contributions to CDA have resulted from SFL (p.11). In addition, both CDA and SFL view

language as a social construct, examining the importance of language in society and the ways in which language has been shaped by society. CDA and SFL also have the same dialectical view of language, the discursive events are influenced by and itself influences the context (Young & Harrison, 2004, p. 1).

Fairclough as one of the founders of CDA has developed a model of CDA. This model was adopted by many researchers in the field of critical linguistic studies. CDA is concerned with how power is exercised through language. Hence it approaches any discourse as a form of social practice. Fairclough assumes that any case of language is a communicative event.

The model consists of three dimensions, they may be summarized as follows:

The first dimension is called the text level (ie description stage), it can be speech, writing, image or mixture of all three forms of communication. This stage analyses a text and describe it at word level.

The second dimension is called discursive practice (ie interpretation stage). It involves production and construction of the text. Approaching any text at this stage encapsulates the interpretation at a text level. This means attention should be given to speech acts, coherence, and intertextuality; these aspects that link a text to its wider social context.

The third and last dimension is called social practice (ie explanation stage). The elaboration of the text provides the standards of the society or the organization. The effect of social structures to be analysed in terms of the norm level.

Figure 1. Diagrammatic representation of Fairclough's critical discourse analysis framework,

Note. Adapted from Fairclough (1995, p. 98)

5. Appraisal Framework

There are three components to the AF: attitude, engagement, and graduation.

5.1 Attitude

Attitude is concerned with human emotions, such as emotional responses, behavioral evaluations, and evaluations of things (Martin & White, 2005, p.35). Affect, judgment, and appreciation are the three subfields of attitude.

5.2 *Affect*

According to Martin and White (2005), the Affect system offers resources for expressing negative and positive emotions (Herman and Silalahi, 2020). These emotions are typically influenced by cultural perceptions of whether a certain emotion is perceived as positive or negative (p.35). Feelings can be stated directly or implied implicitly, as in "I was torn to pieces." The speaker communicates his emotions directly in this statement. Such emotional expressions allow the reader or listener to empathize with the character expressing these emotions. This explicit affect contrasts with implicit affect, in which writers/speakers employ metaphors to infer their emotions, for instance, "He is as cold as ice" conveys that the character is feeling unwelcoming.

Affect is broken into three further classifications, un/happiness, in/security and dis/satisfaction.

1. Un/happiness deals with the feeling of joy or sadness, as in "**The captain felt sad/happy.**"

2. In/security refers to contrasting feelings of peace and anxiety, for instance "**The captain felt anxious/confident.**"

3. dis/satisfaction "deals with our feelings of achievement and frustration in relation to the activities in which we are engaged, including our roles as both participants and spectators" eg. "**The captain felt fed up/absorbed**" (Martin & White, 2005, p.49-50).

5.3 *Judgement*

Judgement is concerned with the resources used to evaluate the intelligence, loyalty, and trust of individuals. Judgement is a semantic resource for evaluating behaviour in the context of institutional norms (Körner, 2000, p.98). Martin and White (2005) proposed that judgement is directed to ethics, capability and social behaviour (p.99). For instance: "**To hit her [the plaintiff] when trying to hit the post would be a very bad aim on the part of the defendant.**" Is a negative assessment of a boy's ability to hit a very close target with a dart (Körner, 2000).

5.4 *Appreciation*

Appreciation includes resources for evaluating phenomena: its value, worth, complexity, and quality (Christie & Martin, 2005, p.24). Consequently, this third field of attitude focuses on the meanings that construct our evaluations of objects, products, performances, and natural phenomena. It can be activated by referencing aesthetic principles and other social value systems, for example in a sentence like 'a beautiful woman' (White, 2020), the process of appreciation focuses on the quality of the woman, as opposed to criticising her for what she accomplishes; hence, a beautiful lady, a gorgeous woman, a prominent figure, etc., are all examples of aesthetic appreciations.

5.5 *Engagement*

Engagement is concerned with evaluations of propositions and proposals, the sources of these evaluations, awareness of other voices and resources for stance taking and intersubjective positioning, as well as the rhetorical implications of diverse positionings (Almutairi, 2014, p.53). Engagement refers to the writer's or speaker's perspective (or stance) on the subject matter. There are two types of engagement: monoglossic and heteroglossic. Monoglossic interaction denotes utterances that convey a concept as a non-negotiable 'given' or 'fact,' thereby excluding dialogic alternatives. Heteroglossic interaction entails formulations that recognize (and permit) multiple perspectives on the text's content.

5.6 Graduation

Graduation is concerned with those values that serve to grade or scale the degrees of positivity or negativity (Korner, 2000, p.108). For example, attitude can be realized by intensity, such as happy versus extremely pleased or happy versus ecstatic.

Figure 2. Appraisal Framework

Note. Adapted from Martin & White, 2005, p.38

6. Data Description

Considering its literary significance, *Blindness* has been chosen for linguistic study via AT. Saramago's work stand out because of his unique writing style and the perspective he employs to shed light on the social perspective when describing the people and events. His writing flows like a conversation since he rarely uses full stops, commas, or capital letters. Saramago utilized this writing style on purpose to give his characters and the world around him a sense of equality (Nevalainen, 2020, p.36). To emphasize, the novel is written in the third person perspective. The narrator is omniscient and frequently gives insights into the individuals' motivations and emotions, as well as forecasting crucial plot points.

Saramago tackles some of the society's most complex and contentious issues in his writing. The story told in *Blindness* is fundamentally about a worldwide epidemic of sudden, unexpected blindness. Nobody is identified, and the novel's setting remains a mystery. In the beginning of the story, a man is suddenly gets blind while on his way home from work, his wife, the doctor, and the "good Samaritan" who drives him home all share the same grim fate. As the "White Sickness" virus spreads and panic and terror sweep the city, the newly blind victims are collected up and imprisoned in a dilapidated, abandoned mental facility (Moore et al., 2008, p.1).

Nevertheless, the doctor's wife, who has not contracted the virus, is a hidden eyewitness within the quarantined hospital. She pretends to be blind so she accompanies her husband (Moore et al., 2008). The story of *Blindness* is one of a society in disarray after a catastrophic epidemic (Esmaili & Zohdi, 2015, p. 2541).

7. Methodology

7.1 Procedures of Data Collection

The current study applies Martin and White (2005) appraisal framework in relation to Fairclough's CDA framework (1989), to analyse 10 extracts from the climax of *Blindness* (3 pages). Saturation, in qualitative data, is when the outcomes of earlier data collection efforts are replicated in subsequent data collection efforts with high frequency. In order to be operationalised in line with the aims and hypotheses much data is collected until saturation is achieved. Since every page of the novel nearly consist of 1000 words, the 10 extracts represent 700 words as a representation sample gathered to reach a mini-corpus.

7.2 Procedures of Data Analysis

This research uses Saramago's *Blindness* as data to demonstrate the efficacy of appraisal as a methodology for interpreting the social implications of varying attitudes. There has never been any attempt to address *Blindness* from a social perspective (ie CDA and AF). In addition, because this research focuses on such literary work (fictional apocalyptic), it contributes to the study of linguistics. The novel sustains ideologies such as the authorial identity, human loss, uncertainty and autonomy. These themes can be studied and reflected through the interpersonal meaning of SFL, particularly AT in cooperation with CDA.

According to Brezina (2018), the data size chosen for a study could consist of thousands, millions, or billions of words. To find significant language usage trends, researchers must carefully evaluate word frequencies and distributions. However, there is no general rule governing the amount of the data; the researcher must determine this, based on the study's objectives and queries. This study selected ten excerpts from the novel's climax as the most representative for appraisal analysis. The following analyses address 10 extracts. It should also be noted that each analysis will be illustrated in depth if the extract carries appraisal, in addition the length of analysis will differ depending on the taxonomies of the extract that relate to AF. The remaining extracts are only mentioned for the purpose of situational context and will be briefly outlined.

The analysis blends both qualitative and quantitative approaches to provide a deeper understanding of the text. The methodological frameworks are implemented using the subsequent steps:

1. Description stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): Marking all the attitudes within the extracts.
2. Description stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): Identifying the voice of each attitude as either heteroglossic or monoglossic.
3. Description stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): Identifying the use of graduation within these attitudes.
4. Interpretation stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): Characterising the attitudes either to be affect, judgement or appreciation.
5. Interpretation stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): Identifying whether the attitudes are negative or positive.
6. Explanation stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): Exploring explicit use of attitudes from the implicit attitudes.
7. Explanation stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): Identifying the use of graduation within these attitudes.

8. Explanation stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): The implications unfolded by the framework tools are interpreted.
9. Explanation stage (Fairclough's CDA framework (1989)): Frequencies, figures and tables are put in order to summarise the results of the analyses.

8. Analysis

Sentences from page 153 to page 155.

1. "If, because of a sudden illumination that might quell his suspicions, the blind man entrusted with keeping an account of the ill-gotten gains of the miscreants had decided to come over to this side with his writing board, his thick paper and puncher, he would now almost certainly be occupied in drafting the instructive and lamentable chronicle of the inadequate diet and the many other privations of these new fellow-inmates who have been well and truly fleeced."

Line 1 is a prediction made by the narrator, which is possible but cannot be predicted with certainty. This discourse carries a judgement/normality. The term 'suspicions' represents the narrator's judgement of the blindman's behaviour. Judgement is also seen in 'ill-gotten gains of the miscreants.' 'Ill-gotten gains' is a veracity (how truthful) while 'miscreants' is a propriety (how ethical). The narrator also demonstrates his negative perception of what the people are confronting via the terms lamentable, inadequate diet, privation and fleeced. This appreciation can be characterized as a reaction because it would be a mental state of quality made by the blindman if he turned to the other side of the ward.

Further, this extract is said in a heteroglossic/expansion/entertain voice because 'may' is but one of several conceivable positions and creates dialogic space for these alternatives (Martin & White, 2005, p.104). Graduation is taken into account by the narrator to intensify the privations that the people are going through. This can be seen in 'well and truly,' which reflects focus and high amplification.

The group of bullies in the third ward in *Blindness* represent the church officials and government ministers when distributing the wealth to the citizens, and when they feel threatened and fear that they will lose their status and power, they will do anything to stay in control. Saramago draws his reader's attention to the lies and evil of the powerful and the truths hidden behind the word 'blindness.'

Portugal, where Saramago was born and raised, has endured eight centuries of monarchical rule, the fall of which has not produced a republic but instead a long-lasting dictatorship. The Portuguese did not obtain a democratic state until 1974, during the Carnation Revolution (Ringel, 2022, p.3). By way of principle, the past regimes and the current one (the time *Blindness* was written, 1995) were opposed by Saramago due to his Marxist political views. Therefore, Saramago criticized the prevailing view of his country. This is vividly drawn by the term 'lamentable chronicle', which entails the long-lasting suffering of the people. In addition, he depicts the inadequacy between the people of power and the citizens (lack of egalitarianism).

The above extract is said in a heteroglossic voice, which entails a prediction made by the writer negatively criticizing the circumstances. Thus, the writer makes room in the heteroglossic background of the text for those who share his pessimistic view of the speech but may believe that this blind man might not change his view, just like the majority who does not

recognize how dire the situation is. Saramago did not use other voices or any inverted comes to reflect alternative utterances. Instead, he used modality as a way of prediction to align the intended readers with his views. Notably, Saramago utilized a high focus of graduation to reflect the significant effect of his people. Another crucial matter which should be noticed is the use of 'if' before the clause "sudden illumination" Gives a sign to the reader that those characters are mentally blind, not physically. Literarily speaking, illumination will help the eyes of the blindman, not his mental sight, but it is the other way around here as the writer makes this light a cleaner for the suspicions of the blind man, which is a decisive fact for causes of white Blindness.

2. "He would begin by saying that from where he had come, the usurpers had not only expelled the respectable blind inmates from the ward in order to take possession of the entire space, but, furthermore, had forbidden the inmates of the other two wards on the left-hand side any access or use of the respective sanitary installations, as they are called."

Line 2 carries a judgement/veracity via the term 'usurpers,' referring to the untruthful criminals who have claimed power by force. Moreover, an explicit judgment/propriety is shown via 'respectable,' portraying the ethics of the blind inmates. This text is heteroglossic/expansion/entertain because of the modal 'would.' This indicates the probability given by the writer to either align the readers having the same perspective or to announce to the others how criminals get control and harm respectable people. Graduation is not present.

The writer makes a probably but uncertain prediction. Saramago makes a claim via the alternative voices and the blind man and the reader is aligned with his viewpoint and stance. He describes people in power as 'usurpers' using force, violence and lies to take control. Saramago utilizes the metaphor, 'the left-hand side,' describing it as toilets to clarify that the Marxist regime is no more than sanitation facilities to the people of power and those following them (blind), which is a clear disalignment with the views of the political beliefs and methods of social democrats.

3. "He would remark that the immediate outcome of this infamous tyranny was that all those poor people would flock to the lavatories on this side, with consequences easy to imagine for anyone who still remembers the earlier state of the place."

9. Appraisal Analysis

The attitude of the line 3 is supplementary where the terms 'infamous tyranny' reveals an explicit negative appreciation of the reaction made by the blind man when he assesses the circumstances. The phrase 'poor people' is judgment/capacity because the subfield of judgment encompasses how we feel about how people behave, whether that behaviour is praised or criticized (Martin & White, 2005, p.42). This passage also embraces a subject 'he,' a modal verb 'would' and a transitive verb 'remark', which reflects a voice that is heteroglossic/Expansion/Attribution/acknowledge. It is read as an acknowledgement because the narrator here dives into the character's feelings and distributes his beliefs. Graduation is not present within the text.

Saramago is a critic by rooting his evaluation in appreciation and judgement rather than in Affect. He also aligns the audience with his stance by adding other voices to convince others with his point of view via voices that are heteroglossic/expansion/attribution/acknowledge. By

criticizing a character or a circumstance, Saramago attempts to form a relationship with his audience by showing his social positioning and convincing others to abhor the current situation (i. e. interpersonal). He suggests that not only would Marxists be put in the lavatories, but “those poor people would flock to the lavatories on this side.” Saramago repeats terms such as ‘lavatories’ throughout the novel to reveal the sickening dictatorship that the Portuguese society faces.

4. “He would point out that it is impossible to walk through the inner courtyard without tripping over blind inmates getting rid of their diarrhoea or in contortions from ineffectual straining that had promised much and in the end resolved nothing, and, being an observant soul, he would not fail, deliberately, to register the patent contradiction between the small amount the inmates consumed and the vast quantity they excreted, perhaps thus showing that the famous relationship between cause and effect, so often cited, is not, at least from a quantitative point of view, always to be trusted.”

A judgment/normality is implicitly utilized by the narrator. Assuming that if the blind accountant would see, he would observe the truth only with his soul “observant soul.” However, the narrator uses the character’s voice within the text which is a heteroglossic/expansion/attribution/acknowledgement. This use is not innocent, we have seen previously that the narrator uses a monoglossic voice to describe the unfavourable circumstances and a heteroglossic voice when it is a positive attitude. In this extract, the narrator presupposes that if this evil criminal accountant chooses to come to the other side and view the world with his soul, he will remark with his writings on the disaster that the blind inmates are going through (describing the norms and ethical side of the society).

The high amplification of the terms “vast quantity” and the low intensification of “small amount” are at stake. Graduation/force/quantification is served here as a tool to the judgement and to unfold the narrator’s perspective that is lying behind the text.

Saramago references the abuse of the working class at the hands of the wealthy elite in line 4, criticizing the economic, social, and environmental circumstances. Marxism evolved during the eighteenth century. Warburton (2011) described the sky of England during this time as being polluted by the factories and the tall chimneys where black smoke clogged the air and caked everything in soot. Men, women, and children worked long hours, typically 14 hours a day. Their earnings were pitiful, and their working conditions were hazardous. They could be entangled in the equipment and lose limbs or even be killed if they lose their focus. There was inferior medical care, and faced with starvation, they had no choice but to work. Many of those who worked in such conditions did not live long lives. On the other hand, the mills' owners made a fortune. They were primarily concerned with making money.

Saramago uses engagement via heteroglossic voice to align his audience to see the truth. By using low amplification, Saramago has described the starvation of the poor and the popular equitation that the cause and effect are not to be trusted. People work for more than what they get. They are starving to death, and no medical care is provided. Saramago is profoundly objecting the ruling power of the Portugal government.

5. “He would also say that while at this hour the ward of this thieving rabble must be crammed with containers of food, here it will not be long before the poor wretches are reduced to gathering up crumbs from the filthy floors.”

The words 'thieving rabble' is an explicit social esteem judgement/propriety made by the narrator as a prediction. This is a consequence of judging people's character as unethical. "The poor wretches" is another social esteem judgment, but it is veracity as a result that it examines the truth reality of the blind people as being sick, weak and unfortunate. Engagement is seen where two facts set the text as a heterogloss. First, the pronoun 'He' is an expansion/entertains use made by the narrator. Second, the modal 'would' is one of a number of conceivable positions and creates dialogic space for alternative positions. Finally, the narrator has not amplified any attitude, which means that resources for adjusting the volume of gradable items are not available in line 5.

Saramago suggests it is due to the economy that the problems in the text have occurred. This reflects his Marxist attitude where all social and political activities, from education to religion to government, are motivated by the desire to gain and retain economic power. As a result, economics serves as a foundation for the rest of the social, political, and ideological realities (Tyson, 2015, pp.51-6). Accordingly, Saramago displays several subordinate power structures that indicate a whole hierarchy, descending from the ruling classes and their institutionalized supporters to various disadvantaged groups. Politicians are the "thieving rabble" crammed by the food and the supporters the 'blind accountant,' and the "poor wretches gathering crumbs from the filthy floors."

Saramago's Marxist influence reflects him being an "unabashed", "unflinching", "unfaltering" true believer of the communist agendas. As a member since 1969 of Portugal's hardline Communist Party, Saramago called himself a "hormonal communist" because he remarked that he couldn't "find anything better" (Jacoby, 2010). According to Tyson (2015), Marxist theory helps us understand history, political events and the current situation (p.51). The fundamental premise of Marxism is to take into account the economic realities of any culture to explain this human culture successfully.

6. "Nor would the blind accountant forget to condemn, in his dual role as participant in the process and its chronicler, the criminal conduct of these blind oppressors, who prefer to allow the food to go bad rather than give it to those who are in such great need, for while it is true that some of this foodstuff can last for weeks without going off, the rest, especially the cooked food, unless eaten immediately, soon turns sour or becomes covered in mould, and is therefore no longer fit for human consumption, if this sorry lot can still be thought of as human beings."

The appraisal analysis reveals that the phrase 'criminal conduct' can be read as a negative appreciation/reaction/quality conducted by the text to denounce the result of the act of those thieves. That is, here, it is an appreciation of the conducted circumstances and not the behaviour which is described.

Another attitude is drawn here by the text 'blind oppressors' as a judgment/propriety, which is a negative expression denoting the behaviour of the blind people who are sick and starving to death. While the words 'sorry lots' entails a normality judgment.

Furthermore, the narrator uses the modal of probability 'would' and the subject 'blindman accountant' to position the narrator's voice to the various propositions and proposals, which means meanings are acknowledged within the diversity of viewpoints put at risk and to negotiate an interpersonal space for his position within this diversity (i. e. Heteroglossic/expansion/entertains). Graduation is not present.

Saramago uses other voices to strengthen his perspective and allow others to take a stance via a heteroglossic voice. The modal verb of probability 'would' is a call to those who have different perspectives. It should be concluded that Saramago is maintaining a relationship (tenor/interpersonal) with both the intended audience and his readers. Saramago is transferring to his audience his negative appreciation to the acts of those in power by the term 'criminal conduct'. In addition, his judgment of their behaviour is brought to the surface by the words 'blind oppressors' claiming that they are nonethical using their power in such an aggressive way to stay in power. He further gives judgment normality, negatively describing those poor people that they should be aware and rise against such acts. This reflects the Marxist aim to make people aware of how they are treated as products of the historical circumstances and of the repressive ideologies that attempt to blind them from this truth to keep them submissive to the governing power system.

7. "Changing the subject but not the theme, the chronicler would write, with much sorrow in his heart, that the illnesses here are not solely those of the digestive tract, whether from lack of food or because of poor digestion of what was eaten, most of the people arriving here, though blind, were not only healthy, but some to all appearances were positively bursting with health, now they are like the others, unable to raise themselves from their miserable beds, stricken by influenza that spread who knows how."

The text in 7 explores an explicit combination of attitudes as it reflects the narrator's affect, judgement and appreciation. To begin with, the phrase 'much sorrow in his heart' visualizes the Affect/unhappiness experienced by the narrator and is transformed to the reader on behalf of blindman accountant, as the narrator calls him within this extract as 'chronicler'.

In terms of judgement, the narrator starts describing the people's behaviour as 'blind', so it is a normality because humans are brought with eyes to see the world and do their needs, and when they lose their sight, they will be unusual. Then he uses a capacity explored by the term 'healthy', and another capacity by the phrase 'positively bursting with health' and the word 'unable'. This is due to the fact that the description entails how capable those people were. While 'their miserable beds' is an appreciation/valuation because it evaluates the value of the phenomena (beds).

In the view of Martin and White (2005) the text can be read as heteroglossic (contraction/proclaim/endorsement), when speakers/writers state their attitudes, they not only self-expressively "speak their mind," but also engage others to endorse and share the thoughts, tastes, or normative evaluations that they are announcing (p.95). Yet, the judgment was intensified by the term 'most', which means the text has conducted a straightforward graduation/force/quantification to demonstrate specific aims.

The social, political, and ideological climate created by economic conditions is referred to as the historical situation in Marxist terms. For the Marxist critic, neither human events (in the political or personal arena) nor human productions can be comprehended without comprehending the precise material/historical circumstances in which such events and productions occur. To put it another way, everything that happens in the world has a beginning and an end. It is impossible to gain an adequate picture of human events by searching for abstract, eternal essences or principles but rather by understanding the actual conditions in the world. As a result, the Marxist understanding of human events and activities emphasizes socioeconomic classes' interrelationships, both within and between societies, and economic power dynamics are used to explain all human activities (Tyson, 2015, p.52).

Therefore, by using the term 'chronicler,' Saramago conveys to us the historical context in which his work was written (heteroglossic/ to align his audience with his beliefs). The people of Portugal were generally healthy while Portugal was the world's dominant power; during the rule of these politicians, however, the majority (graduation used/most) of the population got ill and starved to death. The fact is that innate ideologies of this system tend to blind individuals.

8. "And not a single aspirin is there to be found anywhere in these five wards to lower their temperatures and relieve the pain of their headaches, what little was left was soon gone, after one had rummaged even through the lining of the women's handbags."

Because the above text does not carry any appraisal, it will be substituted by the following (taking into account that the subsequent analysis will trace on the implicit emotions):

9. "Out of discretion, the chronicler would abandon any idea of making a detailed report of all the other ills that are afflicting most of the nearly three hundred inmates being kept in this inhumane quarantine, but he could not fail to mention at least two cases of fairly advanced cancer, for the authorities had no humanitarian scruples when rounding up the blind and confining them here, they even stated that the law once made is the same for everyone and that democracy is incompatible with preferential treatment."

Extract number 9 expresses a judgment/propriety by the phrase "the authorities had no humanitarian scruples". It shows the authorities' ethical side and how violent they were in treating the blind inmates.

Though this extract carries a heteroglossic voice, each represents a different stance. The counter-expectancy of the conjunction 'but' assures the idea that the previous predication given will not be written by the 'chronicler'. However, the narrator assures with certainty that this blind accountant will not fail to remark the two urgent cases 'suffering from cancer'. The use of 'but' as a conjunction or a counter-expectation establishes a connection and engages the intended audience. According to Martin and White (2005), 'proclaim' is used when a text introduces a proposition that is generally accepted, well-known and valid (p. 98). Therefore, this form of interaction is considered a contract because the text limits the possibility of alternate options. In addition, this usage is a concur because the narrator agrees with other voices.

In addition, "they even stated" is a clear heteroglossic voice, but this time it is an expansion/attribution/distance. This is the case since the narrator chooses to distance rather than acknowledge his stance within this claim, and there are no attributions to other uses that invite the narrator to this viewpoint, in the sense that there is no indication of the author's attitude in relation to the proposition.

Moreover, no Graduations or any intensified attitudes are realized within the text.

Saramago, as a Marxist abhors capitalism, imperialism, and classism. That is, his text discloses oppressive socioeconomic factors and invites us to condemn them (including repressive ideologies). A work is said to have a Marxist agenda if it opposes oppressive socioeconomic factors or invites us to do so.

Therefore, one of the most powerful ways in which Saramago attacks capitalist culture is by demonstrating the destructive consequences of capitalist ideology “they even stated that the law once made is the same for everyone and that democracy is incompatible with preferential treatment.”(heterglossic/distancing himself from the claim, as if Saramago is criticizing those capitalists within their own words), in other words, Saramago indicates that the ruling power though saying that everyone will be treated equally, discrimination between social classes is alive, in fact he depicts the country as quarantine and the laws of the country as cancer striking the humanity.

10. “As cruel fate would have it, amongst all these inmates there is only one doctor, and an ophthalmologist at that, the last thing we needed.”

The attitude in 10 is expressed explicitly as an appreciation/reaction/quality by the phrase ‘as cruel fate would have it’. This attitude is conveyed to the reader as a heterglossic/proclaim/pronouncement voice since the whole sentence is declared as a comment made by the blind accountant on behalf of all the inmates in the quarantine and the use of the modal verb ‘would’. However, it should be noticed that the narrator here is not the writer himself but the doctor’s wife. Taking into account that any gradual terms do not intensify this attitude/appreciation.

Aryan and Helali (2012) have stated that the physical blindness Saramago uses in his novel might be used to explain why people have turned away from humanity in favour of brutality. It is pretty evident that Saramago has mentioned a few tips throughout the novel to explain such blindness. The following is an example “It couldn’t be, more likely some infinite weariness, a longing to curl up inside herself, her eyes, especially her eyes, turned inwards, more, more, more, until they could reach and observe inside her brain, there where the difference between seeing and not seeing is invisible to the naked eye”.

The fact of the matter is that Saramago is calling his audience to dive deeply into their souls and brains and observe the actual reality. Going back to the extract in hand, the text reveals (with the use of a heteroglossic voice/contraction/proclaim/pronouncement) the idea that ‘those blind people do not need an ophthalmologist’; It is the last thing they need. What is urgent is those natural ideologies embedded within the society that made those in power strong and fighting to stay in position. Each person should see the world with his mind first and not his physical sight. This is the reason behind making negative/appreciation of the current events; actually, he has agreed to open the space for other positions with the use of probability ‘would’ to either align new people to his side (interpersonal relationship) or let these readers adore such circumstances.

Table 1. *Attitude of Affect Within the First Thirty Extracts*

	Happiness	Security	Satisfaction	Unhappiness	Insecurity	Dissatisfaction
Explicit	0	0	0	1	0	0
Implicit	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	0	0	1	0	0

Table 1 presents the sub-types of Affects. It shows that 1 affect is negatively expressed, while there are null positive affect. However, it is expressed explicitly, while null are implied within the text.

Table 2. *Attitude of Judgment Within the First Thirty Extracts*

	Normality		Capacity		Tenacity		Veracity		Propriety	
	+ve	-ive	+ve	-ive	+ve	-ive	+ve	-ive	+ve	-ive
Explicit	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	3	1	4
Implicit	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	1	2	0	3	0	0	0	3	1	4

Table 2 represents the sub-types of judgement. 14 of the attitudes were expressed as judgement. 3 normality, 3 capacity, 3 veracity, and 5 proprieties. However, most these judgements are negatively expressed (13). 13 of these judgements are explicit, while 1 is implicitly transmitted.

Table 3. *Attitude of Appreciation Within the First Thirty Extracts*

	Reaction		Composition		Value	
	+ve	-ive	+ve	-ive	+ve	-ive
Explicit	0	6	0	0	0	1
Implicit	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	6	0	0	0	1

Table 3 exemplifies 7 attitudes used as appreciation; 6 reaction, 0 composition, and 1 as value. 6 of these appreciations are explicit and 1 is implicit. However, all these 7 appreciations are negatively expressed.

Table 4. *Engagement Within the First Thirty Extracts*

	Affect				Judgement				Appreciation			
	+ve		-ive		+ve		-ive		+ve		-ive	
	Mono	Hetero	Mono	Hetero	Mono	hetero	Mono	Hetero	Mono	Hetero	Mono	hetero
Explicit	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	7
Implicit	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	13	0	0	0	7

As illustrated in Table 4; 22 attitudes are expressed as either affect, judgement or appreciation. Most attitudes are judgements (13), 1 affect, and 7 are appreciation. Noting all of these attitudes are heteroglossic.

(Note: within the above table affect is judged according to positive and negative, and extract 8 has been replaced because it does not carry appraisal taxonomies.

Table 5 summarises the use of graduation across only 3 extracts out of 10. It also encompasses the types of engagement (voices used) within the subfields of graduation. It shows high frequency of focus (4), all these were expressed within heteroglossic voices.

Table 5. *Graduation Within the First Thirty Extracts*

Extract Number	Graduation						Focus	Scaling and Amplification Type	Attitude Type
	Force		Quantification		Focus				
	Mono	Hetero	Mono	Hetero	Mono	Hetero			
1	0	0	0	0	0	1	High focus	Explicit/negative/nudgement/normality Explicit/negative judgement veracity Explicit/negative judgement propriety Explicit/negative appreciation reaction	
4	0	0	0	0	0	2	Low force High force	Explicit/negative appreciation reaction	
7	0	0	0	0	0	1	High force	Positive judgement normality Positive judgement normality Explicit/Affect/unhappiness Explicit Negative judgement capacity Explicit Negative judgement capacity Explicit Negative appreciation valuation	
Total	0	0	0	0	0	4			

10. Results

The analysis consists of 10 extracts that encompass different kinds of attitudes. Each extract may have no, one or more than one attitude. However, 1 of these extracts (nu. 8) does not possess any attitude and has been replaced with an alternative. The remaining 9 extracts showed 22 attitudes. 1 explicit affect, 14 judgements, 1 of these judgements is implicit, and 7 explicit appreciations. Meticulously most attitudes (20) are expressed negatively beside 2 judgements which are positive. On the same line, the voice used is heteroglossic for all these extracts. However, 11 attitudes were amplified and marked a graduation use. It should be noticed that more than one graduation can be used for a single attitude.

Figure 2. *The Realization of Appraisals*

Table 6. *Statistical Analysis of Appraisals within Blindness*

	Attitude	Affect	Judgment	Appreciation	Heterogloss	Monogloss	Graduation	+ve	-ve
The climax Of Blindness	22	1	14	7	22	0	4	0	22

Figure 3. *The Realization Judgement sub-categories*

A key finding showed (as illustrated in figure 3) that the majority of attitudes are 14 judgements. This helps to explain that Saramago is interested in judging the behaviour of the people, society and the circumstances that surrounds him. Figure 3 also revealed that the Saramago is deeply pessimistic, as most attitudes are negatively expressed.

11. Discussion

Based on the frequencies and the statistics above, the analysis shows the following results:

First, all attitudes, affect, judgments, and appreciations are present in the analysed data, although their frequency vary. The narrator highlighted a negative attitude more than a positive one. These findings are consistent with earlier research for example, Khalil and Abdul- Razzk (2020) in their work "Linguistic Evaluation of News Reports on Islamophobic Incidents", They have showed that "the negative attitudes score 97% on the affect scale, 96% on the judgment scale, and 100% on the appreciation scale" (pp.53-4). Wilson's (2011) "AT as a Linguistic Tool for the Analysis of Market Research Interview Data" reached a similar outcome, where he concluded that negative evaluations were roughly twice as frequent as positive evaluations (p.260).

Therefore, to sum up the results, most of the attitudes are negatively expressed. That is, the language of evaluation, attitude and emotion, and the set of linguistic resources position the text's proposals and propositions interpersonally. This shows Saramago's ideological stance with Maxism, for instance we realised in extract 1 how the theme egalitarianism is embedded within the texts (the lack of equality). In accordance with the statistics, judgement has been the highest demonstrating that the narrator is negatively judging either the characters or the whole society. For example, in extract number 2 the text explicitly criticizes the behaviour of the blind inmates being 'unsurpers'.

Second, the results show that the heteroglossic voice has been used more than the monoglossic as shown by the figure below:

Figure 4. *Heteroglossic Sub-Categories within the Climax of Blindness*

Figure 4 demonstrates that the majority of voices consist of the sub-category of heterogloss (entertainment). Since the majority are instances of heteroglossic/judgements – such judgement are attributed to external voices and not only the narrator. Saramago adds other voices into his own narrative. Saramago is emphasising his perspective while simultaneously creating a communicative environment for the purpose of influencing the reader. This is consistent with what has been found in a previous study held by Martin and White (2005) namely “Evaluative key in journalistic discourse – the ‘voices’ of news, analysis and commentary”. They found that the voices change the way the system's meaning-making potential is set up. It indicates that the propositions are rooted in the subjectivity of the textual voice since it contains evaluations of the proposition's probability or evidential basis.

Third, as mentioned above that multiple graduations might be used to strengthen a single attitude. The results prove that graduation has been used in the 10 extracts, which entails those additional meanings can be categorized as either low or high intensity or core or marginal members of a category based on certain values which is illustrated by the figure below.

Figure 5. *Graduation Sub-Categories within Blindness*

The implications of these results confirm that:

The subfield of AT i.e graduation has been used on a great extent to strengthen the negative side of attitude, which reinforces our argument that the negative side has been the focus of the narrator in the climax of the story. This is a clear indication of the ideological stance of the text.

12. Conclusion

This research has demonstrated that AF analysis, in cooperation with CDA, can be applied to an extended fiction text, specifically *Blindness* by Jose Saramago. By applying AF and Fairclough's CDA model (1989) to 10 extracts, the narrator's ideological stance and the discourse representations have been identified. The findings have demonstrated that the majority of the appraisals that are attributed to attitudes in the data are judgments (negative), rather than affect or appreciation. The description, interpretation and explanation stages provided by Fairclough (1989) along with AF proposed by Martin and White (2005) distributed cohort results that unfolded certain themes. The analysis of these results exposes Saramago's Marxist beliefs through the connotations of the apocalyptic genre and the text's rhetorical ramifications. Saramago criticizes the manner in which the government handles issues pertaining to medicine, the economy, and religion. In addition, he calls for egalitarianism and sheds light on how society perceives Marxism. Thus, the current study fills a significant gap in the critical evaluation of fictional texts within the framework of AT. This has made it possible to perform a new and objective examination of a well-known novel such as *Blindness*.

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